

Idea about the composition of the complex, increasing amounts of oxine solution in 5 M acetic acid were separately added to a fixed amount of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) solution in water so that the oxine/hexacyanoferrate molar ratios varied from one to seven. The complex formed in each case was collected in previously weighed sintered gooch crucible, washed with water, dried in vacuum to constant weight and yield recorded. The results are depicted in the curve A of Fig. 1. The results indicate that the complex has the oxine to hexacyanoferrate(II) ratio 4 : 1. The theoretical yields calculated on the assumption of the composition $H_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4 \text{ oxine} \cdot 3H_2O$ (which is confirmed later) is shown in the curve B of the same figure. These two curves not only indicate the composition speculated to be reasonable, but also shows that in the preparation of the complex the yield is almost quantitative and not 70% as reported by the previous authors. The reason for 70% yield is presumably due to the use of proportionately less amount of oxine in their preparation.

Fig. 1. A. Yield in g of the complex formed by adding separately varying amounts of 16.3% oxine solution in 5 M acetic acid to 7.50 ml of solution containing 9.18 g of $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$ in water. B. Theoretical yield of the complex based on the composition $H_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4Ox \cdot 3H_2O$ of the complex. C. Conductometric titration of 50.0 mg of the complex by 0.182 N NaOH solution.

Conductometric titration of the complex by alkali was also done to verify the composition derived from the results mentioned. The complex will be acidic with eight protons [four from hexacyanoferrate(II) acid and four from oxine] per molecule. Curve C of Fig. 1 shows the titration curve obtained by titrating a suspension in 30 ml water of 50.0 mg of the complex with 0.182 N NaOH. The titration curve has two breaks at 30 and 59.5 drops (1.29 and 2.59 ml) of alkali, and the equivalent

weight works out to be 107.3, and hence the molecular weight of the complex 858.4 which is very close to 850.7, the calculated molecular weight of the complex. The two breaks at 1 : 1 volume of the alkali also supports the proposed composition of the complex. The non-linear increase in conductance leading to the first break may be due to the different pK_s of $H_4Fe(CN)_6$ as well as to the progressive solubilisation of the complex during the titration. The chocolate colour of the complex vanishes at 30 drops of alkali indicating that with conversion of $H_4Fe(CN)_6$ to $Na_4Fe(CN)_6$ the complex breaks up into the components. The subsequent linear increase leading to the second break reflects the titration of oxine.

Finally, the element analyses results also confirm the formula $H_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4 \text{ oxine} \cdot 3H_2O$. Found : C, 58.83 ; H, 4.81 ; O, 13.33 ; N, 16.48 ; Fe, 6.63. Calcd. ; C, 59.30 ; H, 4.50 ; O, 13.17 ; N, 16.47 ; Fe, 6.57%. It is to be pointed out that Saha and Saha gave the figures for N (16.75) and Fe (8.54) of which figure for iron is distinctly different from our estimation.

Conclusion : The complex formed between oxine and potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) in acidic medium is very similar to potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) with the potassium ions replaced by protonated oxine cations $[OxH^+]$, and the complex should better be represented as $[OxH^+]_4 [Fe(CN)_6]^{4-} \cdot 3H_2O$. The electrostatic binding between the hexacyanoferrate(II) anion and the protonated oxine cations makes this compound stable towards heat. The yield in the preparation of the complex is almost quantitative and hence this may give a potential method of the estimation of oxine or hexacyanoferrate.

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Electromigration of Some Metal Ions on Filter Paper using Aqueous Glycolate Buffer Media

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THE work on separation of metal ions by electromigration on filter paper has been reviewed by Bailey and Yaffe¹ quite adequately. Complexing

agents of various types have been used for separating transition and inner-transition metal ions⁸⁻⁹. Attempts have been made to use glycolic acid as its aqueous solution to provide potent complexing media for such studies and the results are presented here. As the pH of the electrolyte plays an important part in modifying the migration trends of metal ions, the use of suitably buffered solutions at fixed pH values have been done to study the electromigration of some 14 metal ions by horizontal electro-phoretic method.

Experimental

Aqueous 1, 1.4, 2, 4, 5 and 7% (w/v) solutions of glycolic acid (Riedel, W. Germany) were prepared and used as electrolytes at definite pH values. The pH of these solutions was adjusted with ammonia solution using a pH meter.

Stock solutions (0.1 M) of Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺, Pb²⁺, Ag⁺, Tl⁺, Th⁴⁺, UO₂²⁺ as nitrate and Ti²⁺, Mn²⁺, Hg²⁺, Zn²⁺ as chlorides were prepared from A.R. reagents. Working solutions containing 3-10 µg/µl were prepared by dilution.

The chromogenic reagents employed for detection of metal ions were (a) rubeanic acid, (b) alizarin red-S, (c) chromotropic acid, (d) rubeanic acid/salicylaldoxime/alizarin mixture, (e) yellow ammonium sulphide and (f) potassium ferrocyanide.

Whatman No. 1 filter paper strips of 2 cm x 35 cm were used for electromigration of metal ions at 5V/cm potential gradient for 2 hr. Many separations have been carried out successfully in aqueous glycolic acid media suitably buffered. These have been reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF TERNARY, QUATERNARY AND POLYINARY METAL ION MIXTURES

Electrolyte % w/v	Mixture	Position on paper strip		
		Cationic (-)	Iso-electric	Anionic (+)
Glycolic acid (aq.) 1.14% at pH 4	Fe-Co-Cu	Co Cu Fe		
	Fe-Ni-Cu	Ni Cu Fe		
	Fe-Co-Ag	Co Fe	Ag	
	Fe-Ni-Ag	Ni Fe	Ag	
	Fe-Cu-Ag	Cu Fe	Ag	
	Ni-Cu-Ag	Ni Cu	Ag	
	Co-Cu-Ag	Co Cu	Ag	
Glycolic acid (aq.) 4% at pH 2	Ti-Fe-Co	Co Fe Ti		
	Ti-Fe-Ni	Ni Fe Ti		
	Ti-Fe-Cu	Cu Fe Ti		
	Ti-Fe-Cd	Cd Fe Ti		
	Ti-Fe-Hg	Fe Ti		Hg
	Ti-Fe-UO ₂	UO ₂ Fe		Ti
	Ti-Co-Cu	Co Cu Ti		
	Ti-Co-Hg	Co Ti		Hg
	Ti-Ni-Cu	Ni Cu		Ti
	Ti-Cu-Hg	Cu Ti		Hg
	Ti-Ni-Hg	Ni Ti		Hg
	UO ₂ -Co-Hg	Co UO ₂		Hg
	UO ₂ -Ni-Hg	Ni UO ₂		Hg
	UO ₂ -Cu-Hg	Cu UO ₂		Hg

Table 1 (Contd.)

Glycolic acid (aq.) 4% at pH 2	Ti-Fe-Cu-Hg	Cu Fe Ti		Hg
	Ti-Fe-Cu-Ag-Hg	Cu Fe Ti	Ag	Hg
	Ti-Fe-Co-Cu-Hg	Co Cu Fe Ti		Hg
	Ti-Fe-Ni-Cu-Hg	Ni Cu Fe Ti		Hg
Glycolic acid (aq.) 2% at pH 4	Hg-Ti-Fe-Co-Cu-Ag	Co Cu Fe Ti	Ag	Hg
	Ti-Fe-Ni-Cu-Ag-Hg	Ni Cu Fe Ti	Ag	Hg
	Fe-Ti-Mn	Mn		Fe Ti
Glycolic acid (aq.) 2% at pH 6	Tl-Pb-Hg	Tl Pb	Pb	Hg
	Ag-Tl-Hg	Tl	Ag	Hg
	Mn-Fe-Zn	Mn		Fe Zn
Glycolic acid (aq.) 5% at pH 6	Tl-Pb-Hg	Tl	Pb	Hg
	Ag-Tl-Hg	Tl	Ag	Hg
	Fe-Mn-Zn	Mn	Fe	Zn

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Kinetics of Oxidation of L-Rhamnose by Vanadium(V)

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KINETICS of oxidation of hexoses¹⁻³ and pentoses⁴ by vanadium(V) have been reported earlier. We are now reporting that of L-rhamnose, a deoxy sugar, in sulphuric acid medium.

Experimental and Results

The kinetics of reaction has been studied under the condition [L-rhamnose] and [H₂SO₄] ≫ [vanadium(V)]. Other details are the same as described earlier⁴.

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